

APPLICATION OF MACHINE LEARNING IN ONLINE SHOPPING REVIEW DATA MINING SYSTEM

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Abstract. With the emerging development of Internet and e-commerce, online shopping has gradually become a new consumption mode for people. Consumers leave a large number of comments during online shopping, which reflect their real experience and feelings, as well as contain information about market dynamics and consumer needs. Therefore, how to effectively mine and analyze online shopping review data has become a research hotspot in the field of e-commerce.

Keywords: Data Mining; Machine Learning; NLP; Text Sentiment Analysis; Ecommerce Reviews

1. Introduction

With the rapid development of Internet technology, online shopping has become an important part of Chinese people's daily life. As a valuable information resource, online shopping comments are not only an important way for consumers to express their shopping experience and emotional attitudes, but also a valuable resource for businesses to understand market dynamics and optimize product services. They are of great reference value to both consumers and businesses. Therefore, designing and implementing a system that can effectively mine and analyze online shopping comment data is of great significance for improving consumer shopping experience and market competitiveness of merchants.

This article designs a convenient, easy-to-manage, and fast-running online shopping comment data mining and analysis system for online shopping comments. The system adopts Flask as the back-end development framework, and combines CSS, JavaScript, and HTML technologies to build an intuitive and easy-to-use front-end interactive interface. To ensure the security and persistent storage of data, MySQL is chosen for data storage. In the data collection process, crawler technology is used to crawl online shopping comments, and the original data is preprocessed and Chinese word segmentation is performed. In the data analysis stage, two text vectorization methods, TF-IDF and Word2Vec, are used to extract features from the comment text. Subsequently, three machine learning algorithms, Support Vector Machine, Naive Bayes, and Random Forest, are introduced to classify the comment vectors emotionally, and the classification results of the three models are compared and analyzed. After comprehensive system implementation and test verification, the results show that the system can effectively meet users' needs for data mining and analysis of online shopping comments.

2. Research background and significance

With the popularization of Internet technology and the rapid development of e-commerce, more and more people choose to shop online. Online shopping has many advantages, such as many categories, low prices, and door-to-door delivery. Online shopping platforms such as Taobao, Uzun and Amazon have become an indispensable part of People's Daily life. The emergence of a large number of online shopping platforms has led to the explosive growth of online shopping review data. With the increase in the number of online shopping users, users also generate a large number of commodity review data when shopping. These review data are numerous and cover many aspects, including the real feedback of users on goods, services, logistics and other aspects, which has high research value and is an important reference index for change and innovation in all aspects. And if we want to make better use of these comments, give full play to their value. With the application demand of data mining

technology, in the face of massive online shopping review data, how to effectively mine and analyze these data, extract valuable information, and provide decision support for online shopping platforms, merchants and consumers has become an urgent problem to be solved.

First of all, through the mining and analysis of online shopping review data, we can understand consumers' satisfaction with goods and services, discover consumers' needs and preferences, provide the basis for accurate marketing and product optimization for online shopping platforms and merchants, improve market competitiveness, and reflect its commercial value. This topic discusses and validates the application effect of data mining technology in the field of online shopping, and provides useful reference for the research in related fields. At the same time, it can also promote the technological development of data mining, natural language processing, machine learning and other fields. After that, it is reflected in social value. Through the analysis of online shopping comments, it can provide consumers with shopping reference, help consumers better understand the quality of goods and services, reduce shopping risks, and improve shopping satisfaction. At the same time, consumers can also provide feedback to merchants based on review data, and encourage merchants to improve their products and services. The mining and analysis of online shopping review data can also provide important information for merchants and consumers and promote the development of the e-commerce industry. For example, online shopping platforms can optimize recommendation algorithms based on review data to improve users' shopping experience; Merchants can adjust product strategies according to review data to enhance market competitiveness.

From the dual perspectives of consumers and merchants, this paper deeply analyzes the overall operation of online shopping. This analysis not only helps merchants to understand the advantages and disadvantages of the product, but also can understand the needs of consumers, so as to better upgrade the product iteration and

optimize the business strategy. For consumers, there are a wide variety of products, making it difficult for people to choose. Online shopping reviews can make them more directly and truly understand the quality and advantages and disadvantages of products, and enable consumers to compare and analyze the evaluation of the same type of products from multiple angles, so as to provide a more intelligent choice for their actual needs.

3. Research status

With the booming development of the Internet and e-commerce, online shopping has gradually become an indispensable part of people's lives. In the process of online shopping, consumers will leave a large number of comments, which reflect the real experience and feelings, and contain market dynamics and consumer demand information, which can enable merchants to understand the needs of consumers, so that consumers can choose their favorite products in the chaos of a wide range of goods. This study focuses on the analysis and data mining of online shopping reviews, explores the overall emotional tendency of commodity reviews ^[1], integrates crawler technology, natural language processing technology, machine learning and other technologies, and develops the online shopping review data mining and analysis system based on these research results, so as to help enterprises optimize products more targeted. Help consumers get a better consumption experience.

3.1 Research status of online shopping review data mining

Wu Ruiyuan et al. ^[2] used two text mining methods, LDA topic model ^[3] and emotional tendency analysis, and took the comments of Mi 8 mobile phone in the flagship store of Mi Jingdong as an example to carry out in-depth analysis. After an in-depth data analysis, she made a series of suggestions to JD platform and Xiaomi mobile phone suppliers based on the conclusions. These suggestions are based on her exhaustive extraction of both positive and negative comment topics. To come up with these themes, she used a dictionary of emotions to assess each comment's emotional

orientation, accurately categorizing it as positive, neutral, or negative. She then applied the LDA topic model again to the classified comments, and extracted the positive and negative comments respectively. Before all of this, she did a lot of data preparation: she extensively collected relevant review texts through web crawler technology, and then conducted detailed data pre-processing, including key steps such as word segmentation and removal of stop words, in order to more accurately use the LDA topic model to summarize the review texts into 20 core topics. Xing Fangqi et al. ^[4] used the LDA model and the K-means clustering algorithm ^[5] to identify user emotion on consumer review information including JD.com and Taobao. In the case of Linux-Ubuntu^[6] and R language, this method can obtain more accurate analysis results than a single analysis method. Yang Jun et al. conducted a research on the mining of online reviews of smartwatches, mainly focusing on the mining of attribute-level views and the analysis of the overall emotional tendency of reviews. In this study, we compare the effect of different text representations in the text sentiment analysis of traditional machine learning models, and draw the conclusion that TF-IDF text representations perform best. On this basis, he further conducted experiments to classify the overall sentiment tendency of comments between traditional machine learning models and deep learning models, and the results showed that the deep learning model did not have obvious advantages in text sentiment analysis.

3.2 Research status of web crawler technology

At the 1999 World Internet Conference, S. hakrabarti^[5] first introduced the concept of thematic crawlers ^[6]. Theme crawler is different from traditional crawler, theme crawler is a kind of web crawler that crawls data according to a specific theme or topic, its purpose is to crawl the webpage of a specific theme to obtain information related to the theme, and crawl specific content, rather than generally crawl all the content of the website, while ignoring links unrelated to the theme. An efficient topic crawler can capture content that is closely related to the topic in a very short period of time, while denying access to irrelevant content. This approach significantly reduces

the amount of traffic and document downloads required for local servers to access web servers.

In the development of crawler technology, the Fish Search algorithm proposed by P. Debra et al., realizes the strategy of priority crawling important links by sorting the URL list according to priority. Dr Klenberg's HITS algorithm works iteratively to gradually optimise the search for a particular web page. Although the start of reptile technology is relatively late, its development speed is rapid.

In recent years, Zhang Xiang et al. improved the Bagging algorithm by introducing the aging weight algorithm, thus improving the accuracy of the crawler. Xiong Zhongyang et al. proposed an information self-gain search strategy, which enables crawlers to self-learn and update rules in the crawling process, thus improving the intelligence level of crawlers. These innovations have promoted the advancement of crawler technology, making it more efficient and accurate to serve various information retrieval needs.

3.3 Research status of natural language processing technology

Early milestones in natural language processing include Alan Turing's Turing Test in the 1950s and machine translation experiments at the Georgetown-IBM lab in 1954. Its development is clearly divided into three stages:

The first is the early natural language processing stage. The natural language processing phase is a period of initial exploration and development in which natural language processing relies primarily on hand-written rules. These rules are usually formulated by linguistic experts based on the structure and characteristics of the language, and are used to analyze the text and generate the language. It mainly uses rules to build vocabulary, syntactic semantic analysis, question answering, dialogue and machine translation systems. The advantage of this method is that it does not require a lot of data support and can be quickly put into operation. But the disadvantage is that the coverage is limited and it is more like a small demonstration system. At the

same time, there are still challenges in the management of rules and the scalability of the system.

Next comes the statistical natural language processing phase. With the popularity of statistics-based machine learning (ML) methods, many natural language processing tasks have begun to adopt this approach. The core idea of this method is to use statistical principles, through in-depth training and continuous learning of huge data sets, so that computers can automatically identify patterns and rules in the data, and make predictions or classifications based on them. In statistics-based machine learning, data is key. By collecting large amounts of labeled data, that is, data with known results, machine learning algorithms can extract effective features from it and establish a mapping relationship between input and output. This relationship is obtained by learning statistical rules in the data, so it has high accuracy and generalization ability.

Finally, the neural network natural language processing stage. With the success of deep learning^[11] in speech and image processing, researchers in natural language processing have also begun to pay attention to deep learning. Neural networks are beginning to play an important role in NLP. The main feature of this stage is the wide application and continuous improvement of neural network models, as well as the improvement of big data and computing power, which together promote the rapid development of NLP technology. Since 2014, researchers have tried to directly use deep learning for modeling and end-to-end training. In order to facilitate practical applications, many Chinese natural language processing tools have emerged, such as THULAC, HIT LTP and Jieba word segmentation.

3.4 Research status of text sentiment classification technology

With the rapid development of information technology, especially in the field of big data and artificial intelligence, text sentiment classification technology has gradually evolved into a frontier topic that has attracted much attention from academia and industry. With the popularity of various service applications, the number of review

texts on the Internet has shown a rapid growth trend. These texts contain rich emotional information and potential value. Therefore, the accurate emotional classification of these review texts is of great significance for understanding the real feelings of consumers, improving the quality of products or services, and guiding enterprises to formulate marketing strategies.

In recent years, researchers have proposed a variety of text sentiment classification methods^[12], which can be roughly divided into two categories based on traditional machine learning and deep learning. Traditional machine learning methods, such as support vector machines (SVM) and Naive Bayes, extract text features, such as word frequency, part of speech, TF-IDF, etc., and combine them with classification algorithms to classify text emotions. However, these methods are often difficult to accurately capture the deep semantic information of the text when dealing with complex natural language text, resulting in limited classification effect.

In order to solve the limitations of traditional machine learning in processing text sentiment classification, researchers have turned to deep learning techniques to solve the problem of text sentiment classification. Deep learning technologies, such as Recurrent Neural Network (RNN)^[7], Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)^[7], Transformer, etc. It can automatically learn the deep feature representation of text, thus capturing semantic information in text more accurately. For example, Zhu Haidong et al. proposed an emotion classification method based on EBAP model. This method extracts bidirectional semantic features of text by using the pre-trained model and bidirectional neural network, and further optimizes the features by combining the attention mechanism and the pooling layer of convolutional neural network, finally achieving good experimental results on the Chinese emotion classification dataset.

In addition, researchers are trying to combine traditional machine learning methods with deep learning techniques to improve the performance of sentiment classification. For example, Li Manman et al. built an emotion classification model of

online comments that integrated emotion dictionary and machine learning. The model first used emotion dictionary to initially classify text, and then used machine learning algorithm to further classify text with vague emotion tendency. This method combines the advantages of emotion dictionary and machine learning method, and effectively improves the accuracy of emotion classification.

In addition, the research of Zhu Shaojie and Fan Xiaochao et al. also demonstrated the application potential of deep learning in the field of text sentiment classification. Zhu Shaojie proposed a text emotion classification scheme combined with deep learning features, which enhanced the model's ability to express text semantic information by using semi-supervised RAE method. Fan Xiaochao explored the topic classification and sentiment classification of Chinese text based on machine learning, and on this basis proposed an improved mutual information feature weighting method, which effectively improved the performance of text classification.

4. Research Methods

This research aims to build a data mining system based on online shopping reviews, which can automatically extract useful information from a large number of review data and conduct in-depth analysis and mining. The research content of this project mainly focuses on the design and implementation of data mining and analysis system based on online shopping reviews, so as to provide valuable information for online shopping platforms, merchants and consumers. Promote the healthy development of the e-commerce industry. The main research content of this paper is divided into the following aspects:

4.1 Collection and pre-processing of online shopping review data

Crawler technology is used to collect data, and the comments of products are collected respectively. In product reviews, there will always be some repeated reviews, irrelevant reviews or text data automatically reviewed by the e-commerce platform due

to a long period of time. These review data are not only meaningless to the analysis of the product, but also interfere with the data used in the establishment of the model, affecting the accuracy of the model and subsequent analysis results. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out operations such as text de-duplication, repetition removal and stop word removal, and then use Natural Language Processing (NLP) technology to segment the processed text^[8].

4.2 Establishment of machine learning emotion classification model

Machine learning is superior to traditional classification methods in terms of data processing, adaptive ability, ability to deal with complex patterns, application scenarios and flexibility. Using the machine learning-based sentiment classification method, you can better understand the quality of the review, how much function, the size of the volume and the effectiveness of the brand. This paper will use support vector machine, random forest, naive Bayes and other machine learning classification methods to carry out comparative experiments, to provide support for the subsequent system construction.

4.3 Design and implementation of data visualization and analysis system

The system can intuitively observe the number of good and bad reviews of the product, and can display the recent sales of the product, and can display the words that occur frequently in the comments for word cloud map, and show the correlation diagram between the comments, the system administrator can also see various information of each user. Flask is adopted as the back-end development framework in this paper, and an intuitive and easy-to-use front-end interactive interface is built by combining CSS, JavaScript and HTML technologies. In order to ensure the security and persistent storage of data, MySQL is selected for data storage.

4.4 System test

In the system test, the function and performance of the system were tested respectively. In the function test, the access control, comment collection, text

preprocessing, overall emotion classification analysis and visualization were tested to ensure the normal operation. In the performance test, the system's review crawling speed, data processing speed, accuracy, stability and other performance aspects are tested to ensure that the system can complete the task within the specified time.

5. Conclusion

6. This reserach conducted an in-depth study on the data mining system based on online shopping reviews, which can automatically extract useful information from a large number of review data and conduct in-depth analysis and mining. The research content of this project mainly focuses on the design and implementation of the data mining and analysis system based on online shopping reviews, providing valuable information for online shopping platforms, merchants and consumers. Promote the healthy development of the e-commerce industry.

7. References

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